

Event Abstract

Survey on quality control of pharmacies in Sabratha, Libya

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Background: Pharmacists have critical role in patient's treatment, by ensuring proper dispensing practice, delivering medical advices about possible medical intervention, however if something went wrong the result will be dire, this mistake can be occurred when not pharmacists dispensed medicines in pharmacy.

Objectives: The aim of this study is to determine the quality of service provided by community pharmacists in the city of Sabratha, Libya by evaluating their educational level and their specialty.

Material and methods: This is a prospective cross-sectional questioner-based study conducted among 35 pharmacies in Sabratha city.

Results: The outcomes revealed that 28.5% of visited pharmacies involved physicians and other medical graduated than pharmacists worked in it, which is not their specialty.

Conclusions: The visited community pharmacies were occupied with medical specialties other than pharmacists which exhibit unacceptable and unprofessional practice. There must be enforcement of law to terminate this action that could cause decline for patient safety and health.

Keywords: Pharmacists, Medical Intervention, Low.

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